

Nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of some polycyclic aza ligands

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Abstract : Diethylenetriamine condenses with hexachloroethane in the presence of nickel(II) or copper(II) ion to produce dodecaaza macrocyclic ligand 3,6,9,12,15,18,19,22,25,26,29,32-dodecaza-1,2,10,11-tetrachlorotricyclo[9·7·7^{·72,10}]-dotriacontane (DACD). Further, condensation of the resulting copper complex [Cu₄(DACD)(H₂O)₄]Cl₈ with two molecules of each triethylenetetramine and copper hydroxide yielded a hexanuclear copper complex of the macrocycle 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,21,24,27,30,32,35,38,39,42,45,46,49,52-eicosazaapentacyclo[29·7·7·0^{1,12,0}20,31·7^{12,20}]dopentacontane (EACD). But, in the template condensation of [Ni₂(DACD)]Cl₄ with the triethylenetetramine an additional macrocycle 20,21-dichloro-2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,25,28,29,32,35,36,39,42-hexadecaazatetracyclo[19·7·7·0^{1,12,7}12,20]dotetracontane (DHCD) along with EACD is generated. The products [Ni₂(DACD)]Cl₄, [Cu₄(DACD)(H₂O)₄]Cl₈, [Ni₃(DHCD)(H₂O)₂]Cl₆·3H₂O, [Ni₄(EACD)(H₂O)₄]Cl₈·2H₂O and [Cu₆(EACD)(H₂O)₄]Cl₁₂, and the metal-free ligand hydrochlorides DACD·12HCl, DHCD·16HCl and EACD·20HCl were characterized by elemental analyses, conductivity measurements, melting points and spectral studies.

Keywords : Copper(II), nickel(II), aza-macrocyclic, template synthesis.

Introduction

Previously, we have reported that diethylenetriamine condensed with 1,1,2-tetrachloroethane in presence of nickel(II) or copper(II) (in 1 : 1 : 1, molar ratio) to yield dinuclear complex of hexaaza large-ring macrocycle 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclo-octadecane (HTCO)^{1,2}, where HTCO molecule was generated involving two molecules of each reactant diethylenetriamine and tetrachloroethane. Two larger polynucleating aza macrocycles 2,5,8,11,14,17,19,22,25,28-decaaza-9,10-dichlorobicyclo[16·10·0]octacosane (DDCO) and 2,5,8,10,13,16,19,21,24,27,29,32,35,38-tetradecaazatricyclo[26·10·0^{9,20}]octatriacontane (TTCO) were further generated in the nickel templated condensation between triethylenetetramine and Ni-HTCO complex³. However, the corresponding copper products could not be crystallized. In this paper, we wish to report successful extension of the macrocyclization reaction of diethylenetriamine to hexachloroethane. Unlike 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane system the mode of condensation be-

tween diethylenetriamine and hexachloroethane is changed, probably due to presence of two additional Cl-atoms in the chlorocarbon. A dodecaaza macrocycle 3,6,9,12,15,18,19,22,25,26,29,32-dodecaaza-1,2,10,11-tetrachlorotricyclo[9·7·7^{·72,10}]dotriacontane (DACD) is generated by the template condensation reaction between two molecules of hexachloroethane and four molecules of diethylenetriamine.

The resulting complex [Cu₄(DACD)(H₂O)₄]Cl₈ further condenses with triethylenetetramine in presence of copper(II) yielding a hexanuclear complex of 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,21,24,27,30,32,35,38,39,42,45,46,49,52-eicosazaapentacyclo[29·7·7·0^{1,20,0}20,31·7^{12,20}]dopentacontane (EACD). But, under the similar template condition, reaction between [Ni₂(DACD)]Cl₄ and triethylenetetramine in presence of nickel-ion two complexes one of the ligand EACD and the other of the ligand 20,21-dichloro-2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,25,28,29,32,35,36,39,42-hexadecaazatetracyclo[19·7·7·0^{1,12,7}12,20]dotetracontane (DHCH) are formed (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Reaction scheme.

Experimental

Materials :

All solvents, metal salts, amines and hexachloroethane were obtained commercially and were of reagent grade.

Measurements :

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 820 IPC FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr disks. 1H NMR

spectra were obtained with a Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz FT) spectrophotometer in D_2O solution utilizing DSS as internal standard. The mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-600 spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 KV, 100 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 KV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol was used as the matrix. Visible spectra of the complexes were measured in their aqueous solutions using a Systronic Double

Beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer-2202. Conductivities were recorded with a DDR conductivity meter (type 304)⁴. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Ionizable chloride ions were obtained by conductometric titrations. The metal complexes were decomposed as described earlier⁴ and their metal contents were subsequently determined by EDTA titration⁵.

Synthesis of nickel(II) complex of DACD :

Cyclization reaction involving nickel hydroxide (5.00 g, 53.92 mmol), diethylenetriamine (5.56 g, 53.89 mmol) and hexachloroethane (12.76 g, 53.90 mmol) were carried out in 150 mL butanol. The mixture containing light green precipitate was refluxed for 1 h 30 min. The light green precipitate changed to dirty violet immediately after 5 min and then into a yellowish-brown solution containing a small amount of a brown precipitates after total heating of 1 h. At the end of reaction, a mixture of brown solution and brown precipitate was obtained. The resulting mixture was cooled and stirred for 5 min with 100 mL of water and filtered. The dirty green residue of nickel hydroxide (about 50% of the initial amount) and non-aqueous red layer were rejected. Concentration and evaporation under reduced pressure of the yellowish-red aqueous solution yielded a brownish-violet sticky solid. Sticky material was removed by treating the product with benzene-ether (1 : 1) mixture as described earlier¹. The resulting solid was dissolved in methanol stirred for 10 min and filtered. A green residue in small amount as impurity was rejected. The crude product (as brownish-violet crystals) crystallized from the brownish-violet filtrate was placed on filter paper and treated with a small volume of a mixture of ether/methanol (1 : 1) as described in other systems¹. The filter paper absorbed brown impurity leaving behind analytically pure violet crystals of the macrocyclic product $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DACD})]\text{Cl}_4$, yield 2.20 g (19.12%).

Synthesis of copper(II) complex of DACD :

A 4.23 g (41.00 mmol) diethylenetriamine was allowed to condense with 9.71 g (41.02 mmol) of hexachloroethane in presence of 4.00 g (41.00 mmol) copper hydroxide. The blue reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h 40 min in 120 mL butanol. The colour of the reaction mixture immediately changed from blue to green followed by reddish-yellow and brownish-red within 5, 10 and 20

min, respectively. After 1 h 40 min of continuous heating the resulting solution (brownish-red) was cooled, stirred with 100 mL of water and filtered. A large amount of brown residue was rejected and the greenish-grey aqueous layer of the filtrate was separated from the non-aqueous brownish-red layer. Concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution yielded greenish-grey semi-solid crude product which was further treated with benzene-ether (1 : 1) mixture on filter paper. The resulting sticky product was further dissolved in 50 mL methanol/water mixture (1 : 1) and evaporated at room temperature to yield the deep blue crystalline product $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{DACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8$. The deep blue crystals were finally washed with methanol, followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure, yield 1.34 g (10.80%).

Synthesis of the nickel(II) complexes of EACD and DHCD :

Macrocyclic complexes $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DHCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were derived from $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DACD})]\text{Cl}_4$. A stirred mixture of nickel hydroxide (2.50 g, 26.94 mmol) and triethylenetetramine (3.94 g, 26.94 mmol) in 100 mL butanol was added to refluxed mixture of nickel hydroxide (2.50 g, 26.96 mmol), diethylenetriamine (56.00 g, 53.89 mmol) and hexachloroethane (6.38 g, 26.95 mmol) in 150 mL butanol (refluxed for 1 h 30 min). It was then stirred and heated to reflux for 2 h 30 min. The green initial mixture changed to a brown solution along with a brown precipitate at the end of the reaction. It was then stirred with 100 mL of water and filtered. The yellowish-red aqueous layer containing the products was separated, concentrated and allowed to stand for crystallization. A mixture of reddish-pink semi-solid and violet crystals obtained after 18 days was treated with 50 mL of methanol. The precipitate of pink product $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DHCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ floating with the methanol was separated from the violet crystals of $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by decantation. The decanted part was filtered and the brownish-red filtrate containing the impurities was rejected. The pink precipitate obtained was washed with methanol and dried. Violet crystals of $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ slightly soluble in methanol, were purified by washing with small volume of methanol followed by ether, and dried under reduced pressure, yield 2.30 g.

Synthesis of the copper(II) complex of EACD :

A mixture of copper hydroxide (4.00 g, 41.00 mmol), diethylenetriamine (4.23 g, 41.00 mmol) and hexachloroethane (4.86 g, 20.51 mmol) in 120 mL butanol was refluxed for 1 h 40 min. The resulting mixture containing macrocyclic product $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{DACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8$, described earlier was cooled. Another stirred mixture of copper hydroxide (2.00 g, 20.50 mmol) and triethylenetetramine (3.00 g, 20.50 mmol) in 100 mL of butanol was added to the above mixture with constant stirring. It was then refluxed for 3 h during which time colour of the mixture changed from greenish-blue to green. After stirring the mixture with 100 mL of water, the brown residue, non-aqueous wine-red layer and aqueous blue layer were separated as usual. Concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution yielded impure crystals of the product $[\text{Cu}_6(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_{12}$. Crystals were purified by treating with benzene/ether (1 : 1) mixture on filter paper as described earlier. Deep blue pure fine crystals were washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure, yield 2.20 g (9.94%).

Preparation of the ligand hydrochlorides :

Macrocyclic product $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{DACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8$ (1.50 g, 1.25 mmol), or $[\text{Cu}_6(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_{12}$ (1.50 g, 0.93 mmol) was dissolved in 100 mL water. The solution was acidified with 5 mL conc. HCl (12 N), then H_2S gas was passed into it for about 15 min, and the resulting black precipitate was removed by filtration. Removal of copper was checked by passing the gas again into the filtrate. Metal ion-free, colourless filtrate was concentrated and kept for crystallization for 15 days at room temperature. The resulting yellowish-white flat crystals of $\text{DACD}\cdot 12\text{HCl}$ were washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure, yield 1.20 g (93.36%). A sticky cream colour solid obtained on crystallization of aqueous solution in EACD system was treated with benzene/ether (1 : 1) mixture on filter paper as described in many complex systems. Then the solid was dissolved in 50 mL methanol in a beaker. Colourless fine crystals of the product ($\text{EACD}\cdot 20\text{HCl}$) settled at the bottom were filtered and washed with methanol and then with ether and dried, yield 1.18 g (86.87%).

An alternate method for the preparation of the hydrochlorides of DACD, DHCD and EACD from their nickel complexes was also adopted. The mixture of nickel chlo-

ride and the hydrochloride of DACD, DHCD or EACD were obtained by dissolving 1.5 g of its nickel complex in 100 mL of water acidified with 5 mL of conc. HCl as in the first method. The mixtures was then concentrated to about 30 mL and allowed to stand for crystallization at room temperature. After 15 days, the white flat crystals of DACD (yield 1.60 g (88.24%)) and fine crystals of DHCD (yield 1.05 g (90.37%)) were filtered, washed with methanol, followed by ether, and dried. But, crystallization did not occur in the mixture containing EACD hydrochloride. However, addition of 80 mL of methanol to the uncrystallized solution caused precipitation of a colourless powder that was filtered, washed with a small amount of methanol, and then ethyl ether, and dried, yield 1.14 g (95.22%). The elemental analysis data, C, H, N and ionizable chloride ion for $\text{DACD}\cdot 12\text{HCl}$ and $\text{EACD}\cdot 20\text{HCl}$ are comparable with those for the corresponding products prepared from the copper complexes.

Results and discussion*Synthesis :*

In equimolar reaction of diethylenetriamine, hexachloroethane and nickel hydroxide or copper hydroxide, the tricyclic macrocyclic ligand (DACD) is generated involving two molecules of hexachloroethane and four molecules of diethylenetriamine. The metal complexes $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DACD})]\text{Cl}_4$ and $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{DACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8$ are dinuclear and tetra-nuclear, respectively. Cyclization proceeds by condensation of hexachloroethane with nickel or copper coordinated diethylenetriamine. Each nickel(II) ion is coordinated to six aza donors in an octahedral environment. On the other hand each copper(II) ion in tetracoordinate geometry is surrounded by three aza groups of the macrocycle and one water molecule.

In the reaction of $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_4$ with diethylenetriamine under the similar experimental condition, two molecules of each reactant condense to generate macrocycle 1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaaza-8,9,17,18-tetrachlorocyclooctadecane (HTCO)^{1,2}. Probably, different conformations of $-\text{CHCl}_2$ group of chlorocarbon (**I**, **II** and **III**) allow such condensations. There is free rotation of $-\text{CHCl}_2$ group about C–C single bond where one $-\text{CHCl}_2$ rotates with respect to other. Population of conformation **III** (with two Cl atoms below C–C bond) is 1/3 and that of **I** + **II** (chemically equivalent, each with only one Cl atom be-

low C-C bond) is 2/3. Thus, cyclization through 2 : 2 condensations is favoured over that of 2 : 4 ($\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{Cl}_4$: diethylenetriamine). But, in C_2Cl_6 system (with two Cl atoms always below C-C bond) cyclization is favoured by condensation of two molecules of C_2Cl_6 and four molecules of diethylenetriamine.

The template condensation of triethylenetetramine with the nickel(II)-DACD, or copper(II)-DACD complex in presence of the corresponding metal hydroxide, in 2 : 1 : 2, amine, complex, and metal molar ratio, new metal complexes of the macrocyclic ligands EACD and DHCD are generated. Metal hydroxide-triethylenetetramine complex, formed at initial stage condenses with metal-DACD complex.

The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen elemental analyses for each compound in the Experimental section are consistent with each formulation (Table 1). Percentages of metal ions or ionizable chloride ions also support the suggested formulation. The new macrocyclic compounds

have been further characterized based on the results of conductivity measurements, ^1H NMR, mass, electronic and IR spectra. The most convincing proof for formation of the macrocyclic ligands is obtained from the infrared spectra of the various compounds. Evidence for cyclization is demonstrated by the absence of absorption bands that can be attributed to either free or coordinated NH_2 modes^{4,6-10}. Both the IR spectra for DACD·12HCl or EACD·20HCl prepared by two different methods described under Experimental section, are identical.

Infrared spectra :

DACD systems :

The absorptions at 3170 and 1562 cm^{-1} (assigned to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and $\delta(\text{N-H})$, respectively of secondary amine group) exhibited by the infrared spectrum of the nickel-DACD complex, suggests that DACD is completely condensed macrocyclic ligand. The infrared spectrum indicates absence of bands due to a coordinated water molecule. A weak but very sharp band at 400 cm^{-1} is due to $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration. The $\nu(\text{C-N})$ mode of vibration is seen at 1080 cm^{-1} . The C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring bands appear at 2920 (strong, sharp), 2380 (medium, very sharp) and 1480 cm^{-1} (weak, sharp), respectively. Many other peaks at 1440, 1380, 1320, 1280,

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the macrocyclic compounds

Compd.	Colour (Colour at D.P.)	Yield (%) (m.p. °C)	Λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
				C	H	N	Ni/Cu	Cl ^c
$[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DACD})]\text{Cl}_4$	Violet	19.12	504	28.04	5.20	19.62	13.72	16.66
$\text{Ni}_2\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_8$	(Black) ^a	(270)		(28.13)	(5.21)	(19.69)	(13.75)	(16.61)
$[\text{Cu}_4(\text{DACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8$	Deep blue	10.80	968	20.02	4.35	14.01	21.08	23.63
$\text{Cu}_4\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{52}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_{12}$	(Brown) ^b	(225)		(19.94)	(4.36)	(13.96)	(21.10)	(23.55)
DACD·12HCl	Yellowish-	93.36/88.24 ^e	-	23.22	5.48	16.25	-	41.08
$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 12\text{HCl}$	white	(210)		(23.27)	(5.48)	(16.29)	-	(41.22)
$[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DHCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Pink	-	723	27.30	6.18	19.60	15.31	18.46
$\text{Ni}_3\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{70}\text{N}_{16}\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_8$	-	(235)		(27.23)	(6.17)	(19.55)	(15.35)	(18.55)
DHCD·16HCl	White	90.37 ^e	-	26.84	6.11	17.97	-	45.15
$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{60}\text{N}_{16}\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 16\text{HCl}$	-	(260)		(26.96)	(6.13)	(17.91)	-	(45.33)
$[\text{Ni}_4(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Violet	-	1005	27.98	6.52	20.42	17.17	20.65
$\text{Ni}_4\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{88}\text{N}_{20}\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_8$	(Black)	(253) ^d		(28.10)	(6.50)	(20.49)	(17.16)	(20.73)
$[\text{Cu}_6(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_{12}$	Deep blue	9.94	1080	23.70	5.22	17.35	23.59	26.34
$\text{Cu}_6\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{84}\text{N}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_{12}$	(Blue)	(170) ^d		(23.72)	(5.24)	(17.30)	(23.53)	(26.26)
EACD·20HCl	Colourless	86.87/95.22 ^e	-	26.05	6.61	19.01	-	48.10
$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{76}\text{N}_{20} \cdot 20\text{HCl}$	-	(180)		(26.14)	(6.59)	(19.06)	-	(48.22)

^aDark grey at 290 °C, light grey at 310 °C; ^bbrown at 240 °C; ^cionizable chloride ion; ^ddecomposition, ^eprepared from Cu/Ni complex.

1250, 1050, 1001, 965, 940, 880, 820, 615, 570, 520, 490, 450 and 400 cm^{-1} may be associated with the skeletal vibrations of the whole complex molecule.

In the infrared spectrum of the copper-DACD complex, the medium but sharp N-H stretching modes of only secondary amine groups appear at 3125 cm^{-1} . The compound exhibits $\delta(\text{N-H})$ vibrations at 1582 cm^{-1} . Very sharp bands at 1070 (strong) and 440 cm^{-1} (medium) may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$, respectively. Vibrations for C-H asymmetric (medium, sharp) symmetric (weak, sharp) and scissoring (medium) are seen at 2920, 2870 and 1442 cm^{-1} , respectively. The presence of coordinated water is indicated by appearance of a strong and sharp band at 3220 cm^{-1} followed by other peaks at 830, 620 and 518 cm^{-1} attributed to O-H stretching, rocking, wagging and $\nu(\text{Cu-O})$, respectively.

The metal-free macrocyclic molecule DACD·12HCl exhibits a very strong but very broad band in the region 3200–2800 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{C-H})$. A C-H scissoring peak appears at 1489 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibration for secondary amine is not seen, probably due to its coupling with the strong and broad $\nu(\text{C-H})$ vibrations. A peak at 1605 cm^{-1} may be attributed to N-H bending vibration. A weak but broad band for $\nu(\text{C-N})$ appears at 1110 cm^{-1} .

DHCD systems :

The presence of coordinated water molecules in nickel-DHCD complex is shown by a very strong band in the region 3450–3220 cm^{-1} followed by peaks at 1640 (medium, very sharp), 660 (strong, sharp), 600 (very weak, very sharp) and 580 cm^{-1} (weak, very sharp) assigned to $\nu(\text{O-H})$, $\delta(\text{O-H})$, rocking, wagging and twisting vibrations due to water molecules. A medium but very sharp band at 540 cm^{-1} is expected due to $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$. The characteristics medium bands at 2920 and 2870 cm^{-1} and a strong band at 1460 cm^{-1} are attributed to C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring vibrations, respectively. A medium but very sharp band of $\nu(\text{C-N})$ appears at 1120 cm^{-1} . The medium but very sharp $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and $\delta(\text{N-H})$ bands of secondary amine groups appear at 3150 and 1590 cm^{-1} , respectively.

In the infrared spectrum of the ligand hydrochloride, strong vibration for C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring modes are seen at 2956, 2803 and

1647 cm^{-1} , respectively. The $\nu(\text{N-H})$ for the secondary amine is probably coupled with the strong $\nu(\text{C-H})$ vibrations. However, a medium but very sharp band at 1601 cm^{-1} is attributed to $\delta(\text{N-H})$ vibrations. A medium but sharp band at 1141 cm^{-1} is due to $\nu(\text{C-N})$. Many weak peaks at 2686, 2614, 2435, 2376 cm^{-1} and a medium but broad peak at 1976 cm^{-1} are due to $>\text{NH}_2^+\text{Cl}^-$ groups. Bands at 1298, 1228, 1039, 976, 911, 814, 777 and 509 cm^{-1} may be due to skeletal vibration of the whole ligand molecule.

EACD systems :

A strong and sharp band for C-H asymmetric stretching vibration appears at 2925 cm^{-1} in the nickel complex. The corresponding symmetric stretching and scissoring vibration are seen as a shoulder and a medium but very sharp band, respectively, at 2870 and 1444 cm^{-1} . The bands at 3170 and 1562 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and $\delta(\text{N-H})$ vibrations of the secondary amine group. Another important band at 1140 cm^{-1} is assigned to C-N stretching mode. The bands at 3450–3250 (very strong, broad), 1620 (medium, very sharp), 820 (medium, very sharp), 618 (medium, sharp), 565 (medium, sharp) and 520 cm^{-1} (medium, very sharp) associated with the coordinated water are attributed to $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\delta(\text{C-H})$, rocking, wagging, twisting vibrations of H_2O and $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$, respectively. The $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration is seen as a medium but very sharp band at 430 cm^{-1} .

As expected the $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ mode in infrared spectrum of copper-EACD complex is at high frequency (449 cm^{-1}) as compared to that in nickel-EACD complex, which is due to stronger coordinating behaviour of copper ion. The $\delta(\text{N-H})$ band appears at 1587 cm^{-1} . The weak band at 521 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{Cu-O})$ is comparable with that of $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ in the EACD complex. The other medium or strong bands at 3221, 685 and 627 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{O-H})$, rocking and wagging modes of water molecules, respectively, support the coordination of water in the complex. The $\nu(\text{N-H})$, $\delta(\text{N-H})$ due to secondary amine group and $\nu(\text{C-N})$ vibration are seen at 3138, 1587 and 1144 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The ligand hydrochloride exhibits a very strong and very broad band in the region 3200–2800 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{C-H})$ vibration. The $\nu(\text{N-H})$ band is not seen prob-

ably due to its coupling with the C–H stretching vibration. However, the $\delta(\text{N–H})$ appears as a weak but very sharp band at 1580 cm^{-1} . The strong and weak bands at 1485 and 1171 cm^{-1} are assigned to C–H scissoring and C–N stretching modes, respectively. A few weak peaks at 2729 , 2548 , 2307 cm^{-1} and a medium but broad peak at 1908 cm^{-1} are considered to be associated with $>\text{NH}_2^+\text{Cl}^-$ group as observed in amino acids and their hydrochlorides. Many other bands may be due to skeletal vibration of the whole ligand molecule.

Comparison of IR bands of DACD, EACD and DHCD systems :

The DACD is three-dimensional flexible macrocycle. The low $\nu(\text{Cu–N})$ or $\nu(\text{Ni–N})$ vibration frequency shows that the metal is not encapsulated in the ring cavity because of a large cage size. As expected the $\nu(\text{Cu–N})$ vibration is at higher frequency (440 cm^{-1}) than the $\nu(\text{Ni–N})$ vibration frequency (400 cm^{-1}). Similarly the $\nu(\text{N–H})$ vibration frequency follows the order $\text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+}$. Each copper ion is coordinated to ligand involving its three nitrogen donors (Fig. 1). The fourth coordination position of the metal is occupied by one water molecule. But, in $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DACD})]\text{Cl}_4$ molecule each metal ion is probably surrounded by six aza donors. Either the six donors are in sixteen or eighteen-membered smaller rings. The [16]- N_6 ring system containing bridge combination (2,2,1,2,2,1) appears favourable in comparison of the [18]- N_6 ring system with bridge combination (2,2,2,2,2,2). In the latter unfavourable situation one $>\text{NH}$ group in each ring coordinated to nickel along z-axis (inside the large cavity) will be over-crowded.

The $\nu(\text{Cu–N})$ vibration frequency (449 cm^{-1}) in $[\text{Cu}_6(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_{12}$ on comparison with that in $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{DACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8$ shows that complex forming ability of EACD is greater than the macrocycle DACD. It appears that the additional two [12]- N_4 rings provide more favourable fitting to the metals. Similarly, the $\nu(\text{Ni–N})$ vibration frequencies in the complexes of EACD and DACD follow the same trend EACD $>$ DACD. Also, the $\nu(\text{Ni–N})$ vibration frequencies in $[\text{Ni}_4(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_8 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DHCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are at 430 and 426 cm^{-1} , respectively. The DHCD consists one [12]- N_4 ring less than in EACD.

Mass spectra :

The two FAB mass spectra recorded for hydrochlorides of DACD or EACD prepared by two different methods described under Experimental section, are identical. The highest mass peak found in the spectrum of EACD·20HCl at m/z 1460 corresponds to its molecular ion. But, slightly low m/z value in DACD·12HCl (m/z 1018) or DHCD·16HCl (m/z 1240) may be associated with the mass lost (H) due to fragmentation of molecular ion. The highest mass peaks found in the spectrum of these macrocycles are comparable to those observed in earlier reported aza macrocyclic complexes^{4,9}. A representative mass spectrum of DACD·12HCl is given in Fig. 2.

The fragmentation pattern of molecular ions of DACD·12HCl and EACD·20HCl systems are also in support of the structures of the two macrocycles. Many peaks at m/z 916, 880, 839, 808, 772, 739, 698, 664 and 592 (Fig. 2) are due to successive loss of 3, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1 and 2 HCl molecules. Similar peaks at m/z 1316, 1244, 1208, 1172, 1028, 992, 956, 920, 884, 844, 812, 778 and 740 in mass spectrum of EACD·20HCl (Fig. omitted) indicate loss of 4, 2, 1, 1, 4, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1 and 1 HCl molecules. The last HCl-free fragments are : $\text{DACD}^+ (\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_4)^+$ and $\text{EACD}^+ (\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{76}\text{N}_{20})^+$. Their existence in the corresponding mass spectrum (as metal-free macrocycles in case of metal complexes^{11–14}) also confirms the structure of the ligand hydrochloride.

Further, peaks below m/z 592 and 740 in the mass spectra of DACD·12HCl and EACD·20HCl, respectively, are also in structural support of the assigned fragments. The fragmentation pattern for DACD^+ ion is shown in Fig. 3. The different fragments and their masses are : 543 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_3 - 2\text{H}$)⁺, 579 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_3 - \text{H} + \text{Cl}$)⁺, 613 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_{12}\text{Cl}_3 - 2\text{H} + 2\text{Cl}$)⁺, 563 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{43}\text{N}_{11}\text{Cl}_3 - 2\text{H} + \text{Cl}$)⁺, 460 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_{10}\text{Cl}_3 + \text{H}$)⁺, 520 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_{10}\text{Cl}_3 + 3\text{H} + \text{NH}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}$)⁺, 443 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_9\text{Cl}_3 - \text{H}$)⁺, 482 ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_9\text{Cl}_3 + 3\text{H} + \text{Cl}$)⁺, 367 ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_7\text{Cl}_2$)⁺, 425 ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{37}\text{N}_9\text{Cl}_2$)⁺, 440 ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_{10}\text{Cl}_2$)⁺, 237 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2 - \text{H}$)⁺, 273 ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2 + \text{Cl}$)⁺, 176 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2 - 4\text{H}$)⁺, 214 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2 - \text{H} + \text{Cl}$)⁺, 137 ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{NCl}_2$)⁺, 108 ($\text{C}_2\text{HNC}_2 - \text{H}$)⁺, 390 ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{Cl}_4$)⁺ and 329

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of DACD.12HCl.

$(C_{11}H_{21}N_5Cl_3 + H)^+$. There are two different structures, depending upon the mode of cleavage, for the fragments at m/z 237 or 176 as shown in Fig. 3.

The described fragment ions arising from thermal cleavage of the HCl-free EACD⁺ ion (Fig. omitted) are also favoured by the m/z peaks of the mass spectrum. The fragment ions at different m/z values are summarized as : 721 ($C_{32}H_{75}N_{19} - 4H$)⁺, 661 ($C_{30}H_{69}N_{17} - 6H$)⁺, 618 ($C_{28}H_{64}N_{16} - 6H$)⁺, 592 ($C_{26}H_{60}N_{16} - 4H$)⁺, 551 ($C_{24}H_{55}N_{15} - 2H$)⁺, 496 ($C_{22}H_{49}N_{13} + H$)⁺, 468 ($C_{20}H_{45}N_{13} + H$)⁺, 447 ($C_{20}H_{44}N_{12} - 5H$)⁺, 391 ($C_{18}H_{38}N_{10} - 3H$)⁺, 281 ($C_{13}H_{27}N_7$)⁺, 232 ($C_{10}H_{22}N_6 + 6H$)⁺, 211 ($C_{10}H_{21}N_5$)⁺, 181 ($C_9H_{20}N_4 - 2H$)⁺, 157 ($C_7H_{16}N_4 + H$)⁺ and 113 ($C_5H_{11}N_3$)⁺. These ions are generated by successive loss of $NH(CH_2)_2NH$, $NHCH_2CH_2$, CH_2CH_2 , $NHCH_2CH_2$, $NH(CH_2)_2NH$, CH_2CH_2 , NH , $NH(CH_2)_2NH$, $CNH(CH_2)_2NH(CH_2)_2NH$, $CNHCH_2CH_2$, NH , CNH , CH_2CH_2 and $NHCH_2CH_2$ from $(C_{32}H_{76}N_{20})^+$.

¹H NMR spectra :

The PMR spectrum of DACD hydrochloride can be resolved into three distinct regions attributed to NH_2^+ and two non-equivalent CH_2 protons. It shows a broad singlet at 4.99 ppm assigned to NH_2^+ resonances. The remaining two signals for non-equivalent CH_2 protons

are broad triplets centered at 3.47 and 3.55 ppm (J 6.00 Hz). The first triplet resonance is attributed to the CH_2 protons near to Cl atom whereas the second resonance is assigned to the remaining CH_2 protons. The relative areas of the two triplets being identical correspond to the expected protons. The PMR spectrum of EACD hydrochloride differs in several respects from that of DACD. It can be resolved into two regions, which correspond to the presence of NH_2^+ and CH_2 protons. A singlet at 4.78 ppm and a broad multiple in the region 3.63–3.09 ppm are ascribed to NH_2^+ and CH_2 protons, respectively. A broad singlet at 4.68 ppm in nickel-DACD complex may be assigned to NH proton resonance. Slightly upfield from the NH resonances complex multiples in the region 3.54–2.80 are ascribed to the methylene protons.

Electronic spectra :

A majority of nickel(II) complexes of the tetraaza macrocycles reported in literature^{7,15-17} are square planar. But, those of few large ring macrocycles^{18,19} and cage systems consisting of additional aza donors²⁰ and ligands of pendant donors¹⁵ are octahedral. Formation of an octahedral complex also depends upon the nature of the axial ligand present in the reaction mixture⁷. The electronic spectrum of nickel(II) complex of the tri, tetra or pentacyclic ligand exhibits three broad bands at 800–

Fig. 3. Fragmentation pattern of DACD⁺ ion.

781, 558–515 and 357–341 nm. The bands are attributed to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ of

octahedral nickel(II)²¹. The visible spectra of copper(II) complexes of DACD and EACD also show broad bands

(single) at 534 and 505 nm, respectively as reported for rectangular copper(II) tetraaza macrocycles^{22,23} in solution. Here, a copper ion is coordinated to either four N-donors or three N-donors and one O-donor in a plane.

Solubility, conductivity and other data :

All the compounds being ionic in nature are highly soluble in water. Their solubility is comparatively much low in other polar solvents like methanol, ethanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. The molar conductivity of the complexes and the number of ionizable chloride ion in all macrocyclic molecules recorded in Table 1, are in support of their ionic structures. The complex $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{DACD})]\text{Cl}_4$ is 4 : 1 electrolyte exhibiting molar conductance value $504 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$.

The molar conductance value $723 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ determined for $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DHCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is consistent with a 6 : 1 electrolyte. The complex copper-DACD or nickel-EACD is 8 : 1 electrolyte. The conductivity value of $1080 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $[\text{Cu}_6(\text{EACD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_{12}$ is consistent with 12 : 1 electrolytes. The nickel complexes are violet/pink while the copper complexes are deep blue. The metal-free ligand hydrochlorides DACD·12HCl and EACD·20HCl are yellowish-white and colourless, respectively. All the compounds are thermally stable. The 3 and 2 lattice water molecules of nickel complexes of DHCD and EACD, respectively, are lost on heating these complexes at 120 °C. The remaining water molecules including those of copper complexes of DACD and EACD, which are not lost below 120 °C, are coordinated to metal ion. The macrocyclic molecules are thermally stable. The complex molecules, except the nickel and copper complexes of EACD that decompose at 253 and 170 °C, respectively, melt above 200 °C. The copper complex of DACD decomposes at 240 °C. However, the corresponding nickel complex is decomposed to a dark grey compound at 290 °C, and then to a light grey compound at 310 °C. Hydrochlorides of DACD, EACD and DHCD melt at 210, 180 and 260 °C, respectively.

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